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Effects of working capital management on corporate profitability in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigates the effects of working capital management on corporate profitability of Nigerian pension fund administrations. Unlike previous studies that was done on cement firms; manufacturing firms; brewery firms food and beverages firms; pharmaceutical firms and so on. The present study examines how working capital management and its interactions with current ratio, quick ratio and total debt to total assets has impacted on corporate profitability from 2012 to 2014. The study used a sample of 21 licensed pension fund administrations in Nigeria. In analyzing the data, the study adopted panel multiple regression to identify the possible effects of their working capital management on the corporate profitability of licensed pension fund administrators while we interpreted fixed effect analysis after using Hausman test. Preliminary analyses also conducted such as descriptive statistics and correlation matrix. The result showed that working capital management had a significant and positive influence on pension fund administrators' corporate profitability. However, when interacted with current ratio and quick ratio, it was revealed that working capital management of pension fund administrators positively and significantly influences corporate profitability at 10%. In the case of total debt to total assets interaction with corporate profitability, the study also shows positive and significant impact on corporate profitability at 1%, meaning that Nigeria pension administrators have a minimum risk associated with working capital operations through the commission investment guideline. The minimum risk shows that administrators have the ability to pay off its liabilities with its assets. The study recommends that administrators should continue to utilize its working capital efficiently to increase profitability, pay its short-term and long-term obligations while maintaining minimum risk with its assets.

Keywords: corporate capital management, current ratio, quick ratio, total debt to profitability, working total assets

1. Introduction

Working capital management of corporate entities is most crucial in attaining optimal liquidity position and in ensuring corporate going concern. It is one of the most important decisions for companies when making a trade-off between liquidity and profitability, perhaps, in a way that optimizes the amount and composition of their current assets and how they are financed (Eljelly, 2004). The way a firm manages its working capital could significantly affect its profitability (Deloof, 2003; Raheman and Nasr, 2007). Decisions relating to working capital involve managing relationships between a firm's short-term assets and liabilities to ensure that a firm is able to continue its operations, and have sufficient cash flows to satisfy both maturing short-term debts and upcoming operational expenses at minimal costs, and consequently, increasing corporate profitability (Angahar and Agbo 2014).

Many studies have been done on the working capital management on corporate profitability in Nigeria. For example Ajibolade and Sankay, 2013, Owolabi and Alu 2012, Ikpefan, Ailemen and Owolabi 2014 on manufacturing firms; Angahar and Agbo, 2014 on cement industry; Ani, Okwo and Ugwunta 2015 on brewery firms; Olufemi and Olubanjo 2009 on selected quoted companies; Ojeani 2010 on pharmaceutical firms, Osundina 2014 on food and beverages firms. While some like Zahra and Azam, (2012) studied Iran

companies; Abbasali and Milad (2012) studied Tehran companies; Kulkanya 2012 studied Thai companies. However, most of these prior studies were done in Nigeria as well as in other countries and none have been done in Nigeria pension industry to the best of our knowledge.

Uremadu et al. (2012) investigated on the effect of working capital management and liquidity on corporate profits among Nigeria firms using 25 manufacturing companies for the period of two years. The result shows that working capital management and liquidity had a significant effect on corporate profitability, which the influences are either negative or positive. Owolabi and Alayemi (2010) found that there is a strong effect of working capital (especially in terms of whether the company adopted an aggressive or conservative approach in managing their working capital) on profitability of a Nigerian manufacturing firm. Almazari (2013) in his study on effects of working capital management and liquidity on profitability using Saudi Arabia firms, reported positive and significant effect of working capital management on profitability. Shin and Soenen (1998) worked on the effects of liquidity on profitability. The result shows a negative and significant effect of liquidity on profitability.

In summary since working capital is the excess of current assets over current liabilities, it can simply be put as the cash available at hand for the day-to-day running of the firm. Nigeria pensions fund

administrators has the obligation to pay retirees from investment asset while maintaining optimal profitability for going concern. This resulting probability whether working capital management affects corporate profitability of pensions fund administrators to meet their daily functions especially paying retirees for life create gap for this research. The study therefore intends to fill the gap using pensions fund administrators to see if the result of the study will be the same with that of prior studies arising from different sectors and countries. The main aim of the study is to determine the effects of working capital management on corporate profitability among licensed pensions fund administrators in Nigeria, while specific objectives are:

1. to determine the effects of current ratio on corporate profitability;
2. to ascertain the effects of quick ratio on corporate profitability; and
3. to find out the effects of total debt to total assets on corporate profitability

Research Hypotheses

A set of null hypotheses were formulated for the study as follows:

1. There is no significant effect of current ratio on corporate profitability of Nigeria pensions fund administrators.
2. There is no significant effect of quick ratio on corporate profitability of Nigeria pensions fund administrators.
3. There is no significant effect of total debts to total assets on corporate profitability of Nigeria pension's administrators.

Scope of the Study

The study covers 21 licensed pensions fund administrators by National pensions commission in Nigeria from 2012 to 2014 using their published financial statements.

The remaining sections of the paper are organised as follows. Section 2 briefly reviews empirical literature on corporate profitability. It discusses its effect on working capital management. The research design is described in section 3. While section 4 presents and discusses the empirical findings. Section 5 provides a summary of the results, conclusion and recommendations.

2. Review of related literature

Conceptual framework

Every business is mostly concerned with its profitability; they defined profitability as the ability to make profit from all the business activities of an organization, company, firm, or an enterprise. Additionally, it shows how efficiently the management can make profit by using all the resources available in the market. One of the most frequently used tools of financial ratio analysis is profitability ratios, which are used to determine the company's bottom line (Rahema et al., 2011)

Rahema et al., (2011) worked on sector-wise performance of working capital management and reported that profitability ratios show a company's overall efficiency and performance using measures and profitability ratio analysis. They added that profitability and management efficiency are usually taken to be positively associated: poor corporate profitability affects management efficiency and vice

versa. The result shows that working capital management has positive and significant effects on corporate profitability as wealth maximization and investment in current assets is made only if an acceptable return is obtained. While liquidity is needed for a company to continue business to meet its current needs.

According to Pandey 2005 “companies with higher amounts of assets should be able to earn higher levels of income. Return on assets expresses the net income earned by a company as a percentage of the total assets available for use by that company. It measures management ability to earn a return on the firm’s resources”.

Lazaridis and Tryfonidis (2006) worked on the effects of working capital management on corporate profitability using listed companies in the Athens Stock Exchange of 131 firms for the period 2001-2004. The results indicated a statistical significant positive effect of working capital management on corporate profitability, meaning that managers could create value for shareholders by handling correctly the cash conversion cycle and by keeping each different component to an optimum level.

Owolabi and Alayemi (2010) in their study of working capital as a financial strategy using Nestle Nigeria, their result shows a strong and negative relationship between the working capital (especially in terms of whether the company adopted an aggressive or conservative approach in managing their working capital) and the profitability of a Nigerian manufacturing firm

The notion of performance has been approached over the years in numerous

studies and analyses, and in the academic writings, the concept of “performance” is associated with the concepts of “profitability”. In most of the studies, profitability is expressed by three representative indicators; namely return on assets, return on equity and net margin (Tomuleasa and Cocris 2014). In this respect, we can observe the following papers, which considered at least one of the mentioned variables: Bourke (1989), Staikouras and Wood (2004), Park and Weber (2006), Pasiouras and Kosmidou (2007), Athanoglou et al. (2008), Albertazzi and Gambacorta (2009), Millon Cornett et al. (2010), Dietrich and Wanzenried (2011), Kanas et al. (2012), among others. The study used return on assets to measure profitability in order to ascertain pension fund administrator return on their available funds.

Theoretical framework

The study is anchored on the portfolio theory, developed initially by Harry Markowitz in the early 1950 on attempt to quantify the relationship between risk and return. It provides some of the theoretical foundations for asset allocation and investing in index mutual funds. Expected rates of return for various asset classes are evaluated and compared to the risk of the asset classes. The goals and risk tolerance of the investor determine the trade-off between the expected return and risk of the portfolio. The portfolio is constructed by combining various lower-risk and higher-risk asset classes to achieve an efficient risk-return trade-off.

Determining risk tolerance is a critical step in designing a portfolio. A number of approaches have been developed to aid the investor in assessing risk tolerance.

Both shorter-term risk and longer-term risk are characterized by the uncertainty of returns. Shorter-term risk typically is characterized by the uncertainty of shorter-term returns; e.g., monthly or annual returns. Longer-term risk is better characterized by the uncertainty of the cumulative portfolio value (terminal wealth) after many years of investing.

Therefore, pension fund administrators' corporate profitability has a responsibility to protect the interest of contributors, to enable administrators pay retiree for life. The goals and risk tolerance of the administrators as to assets investment will be minimized in order to achieve a portfolio of high investment return with the National pension's commission investment guidelines through efficient working capital management.

Empirical Review

Tomuleasa & Cocris, V. (2014) investigated the major determinants of bank performance in the European banking sector, taking into consideration the most important financial groups from this region. They applied two fixed-effects regression models to a panel of European banks that covers the period 2004-2012, where profitability was assessed through two variables, namely return on average equity and net interest margin. Their results show that all bank-specific determinants affect bank profitability significantly, but not always in the anticipated way, reporting that the business cycle has a positive, albeit asymmetric impact on bank profitability, suggesting that profitability is pro-cyclical.

The effect of current ratio on corporate profitability

Sing and Penny (2008) worked on the effects of working capital management on corporate profitability using Hindalco Industries Ltd during the years 1990-2008. The result shows that current ratio, acid test ratio had positive and significant effects on corporate profitability.

Binti and Mohd saads' (2010) in Pouraghajan and Emamgholipourarchi (2012) investigated on the effects of working capital management on profitability and market evaluation. They examined 65 companies in Pakistan between 2005 and 2009 using current ratio as measure to working capital management criteria and return on invested capital ratio as a criterion of company's profitability. The result showed significant correlation between working capital and value of profitability of the company and concluded that Pakistani companies correlated heavily on current assets to maximize profits.

Ikpefan, Ailemen and Owolabi (2014) focused on the effect of working capital management on profitability using Nestle Nigeria Plc and Cadbury Nigeria Plc. They used correlation and regression analysis to analyzed quick ratio as measure to liquidity. Current ratio, trade receivable collection and trade payables payment periods were used as efficiency variables to capture the working capital management policy adopted by these companies while return on equity was used as the profitability variable. The result found a negative and significant effect of working capital management on profitability of Nestle Nig. Plc, while it found a positive and significant effect of working capital management on corporate profitability of Cadbury Nig. Plc. They recommend that

companies should manage their working capital efficiently by upgrading the quality of their assets while obsolete inventories should be written off.

The effect of quick ratio on corporate profitability

Smith and Begemann (1997) investigated the effects of working capital management on return on investment using industrial firms listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange. They used multiple regression to test the effects of quick ratio on return on investment. The result shows a positive significant effect of quick ratio on return on investment of firms listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange.

Ajibolade & Sankay (2013) focused on the effect of working capital management on financing decision: synergetic effect on corporate profitability using 35 manufacturing listed companies in Nigeria. They examined working capital using quick ratio in contrast to studies that used several proxy variables including current ratio, average collection period, inventory turnover. The result found a positive significant effect of working capital management on debt structure and profitability, but insignificant effect on working capital composition on corporate profitability of Nigeria manufacturing firms.

The effect of total debt to total assets on corporate profitability

Abbasali and Milda (2012) focused on the effects of working capital management on profitability and market evaluation using companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange for a period from 2006 to 2010. Return on assets and return on invested

capital ratio were used to measure the profitability of firms, while they Tobin Q ratio to measure the market value of companies. They study measured working capital management criteria using total debt to total assets ratio. Their result indicates that there is a significant effect of working capital management on profitability criteria of company but insignificance effects with the criterion of market value of company.

Gill, et al., (2011) worked on the effect of capital structure on profitability using 272 American firms listed on New York Stock Exchange for a period of 3 years from 2005 – 2007. The correlations and regression analyses used to estimate the functions relating to profitability (measured by return on equity) with measures of capital structure. Their result shows a positive effect of total debt to total assets on corporate profitability in the service industry. However, they reported a positive effect of total debt to total assets on profitability in the manufacturing industry.

Abdul (2010) on the effects of capital structure on firm's performance using 36 engineering sector firms in Pakistani during the period 2003-2009. The result shows that total debt to total assets has a significantly negative effect with the firm performance on measured by return on assets.

Based on these results done at different environment that this research is aims at filing the gap in Nigeria pensions industry. In summary, if working capital management influences firm profitability, and through effective working capital management, organizations will meet its current needs. We predict positive

significant effect of working capital management on corporate profitability.

3 Research Methodology

Research Design

The study is of an ex post facto design. We use secondary data by obtaining financial information covering all licensed pensions fund administrators by National pension's commission from 2012 to 2014. Data were obtained from their annual reports of the sampled administrators.

The selection of the variables (regressand and regressor) is primarily guided by the results of previous empirical studies and the available data. The dependent and independent variables are defined so that they are consistent with those previous empirical studies while the uniqueness of the present study lies in its inclusion of all licensed pensions fund administrators in Nigeria as part of its data.

Population of the study

The population of this study is made of all the Nigerian companies that are categorized under financial sector. However, both quoted or not quoted in the Nigeria stock exchange market.

Sample size of the study

The population of this research is made up all 21 licensed pensions fund administrators by National pension commission. We create an unbalanced panel for 2012, 2013 and 2014 for licensed pensions fund administrators by National pension's commission in Nigeria.

Estimation procedure

The assumption in panel data regression is that the dependent variable is a linear function of the independent variables with consideration to heterogeneity in the pooled pension's administrators. This means that pooled regression assumed that there is no difference in the pooled pension's administrators while panel regression assumed cross-section heterogeneity (cross section fixed effect) and period heterogeneity (time fixed effect).

Model Specification and Measurement of Variables

In specifying our panel regression model for the effects on corporate profitability, our major variables are current ratio (CurRatio), quick ratio (QuickRatio) and total debt to total assets (ToDebtAsst). Also included in the model are cross-section (Pensions fund administrator) and years (2012 – 2014) in the panel regressions.

The panel multiple regression with an error term (μ_i) is expressed in equation

$$CorProf_{it} = f (CurRatio + QuickRatio + ToDebtAsst) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$CorProf_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 CurRatio_{it} + \beta_2 QuickRatio_{it} + \beta_3 ToDebtAsst_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where

α_i = constant

Dependent Variable

CorProf = Corporate profitability; following Pouraghajan & Emamgholipourarchi (2012) proxy by return on asset is an indicator of how profitable a company is relative to its total

assets. It gives an idea as to how efficient management is at using its assets to generate earnings, calculated by dividing a company's annual earnings by its total assets. We calculated return on asset as earnings before interest and taxes/ total asset.

Independent Variables

CurRatio = current ratio; following Pouraghajan & Emamgholipourarchi (2012) we measure the influence of current ratio through pension administrators current ratio. The ratio states: the ability of a pensions administrators to pay its short term and long term obligations, which calculated by current assets divided by current liabilities. This ratio was also used by Sing & Penny (2008), Ikpefan., Ailemen & Owolabi (2014). The apriori sign is $\beta_1 > 0$

QuickRatio = quick ratio: following Arshad & Gondal (2013), Gomes (2013) we measure the influence of quick ratio through pension administrators' quick ratio. The ratio states: the administrators' ability to meet its short-term obligations with its most liquid assets, which calculated by cash and equivalents plus marketable securities plus accounts receivable divided by current liabilities. The apriori sign is $\beta_2 > 0$

Data Description and Analysis

Table 4.1

Descriptive Statistic					
Variables	Mean	Max	Min	Std. Dev	JB (P-Value)
ROA	0.16	1.04	- 0.71	0.24	35.10 (0.00)*
CURRATIO	4.59	29.68	0.00	6.23	131.30 (0.00)*
QUICKRATIO	4.57	29.50	0.00	6.19	132.33 (0.00)*
TODEBT2TOASS	0.24	2.08	0.00	0.36	439.49 (0.00)*
No of Cross-section	21				
All data observations	63				

Source: Author (2016)

NOTE *1% level of significance, ** 5% level of significance and ***10% level of significance

ToDebtAsst = Total Debt to total asset: following Abbasali & Milda (2012). We measured the total debt to total asset. TD/TA = Total Debt/Total asset. When measuring the leverage ratio that defines the total amount of debt relative to assets of administrators. It enables comparisons of leverage to make across different administrators. The higher the ratio, the higher the degree of leverage and financial risk among administrators. The apriori sign is $\beta_3 < 0$

4. Data presentation and analysis

In this study, we investigate the effects of working capital management on corporate profitability of licensed pension administrators in Nigerian. A sample of 21 licensed pension administrators from which 63 observations were made; To ensure adequate observation for statistical testing, we adopted a panel data analysis to identify the possible effects on the corporate profitability. We conducted descriptive statistics and correlation matrix. Pooled and panel regression with fixed and random effect panel data regression and the Hausman test were also conducted to select between fixed and random effect models.

Table 4.1 shows the mean (average) for each of the variable, their maximum values, minimum values, standard deviation and Jarque-Bera (JB) statistics (normality test). The results in table 4.1 provided some insight into the nature of licensed pension administrators in Nigerian that were used in the study. Firstly, the difference between the maximum and minimum values of current ratio shows the ability of pension administrators to pay their short-term and long-term obligations. Secondly, it was observed that on the average over the three year period (2012 – 2014), the pension administrators used its assets to generate earnings of 0.16. We also observed that the return on asset over the period was 1.04 maximum while the minimum stood at -0.71. This shows that pension administrators' efficient management are different by using its assets to generate earnings for its contributors, retiree and investors. These wide variations in return on assets therefore justify the need for this study, as we expect some administrators to generate more earnings using their working capital management. Our sampled administrators are heterogeneous due to panel data. The panel analysis accommodates times as well as the heterogeneity effect of the administrators, which may be random or fixed.

Lastly, in table 4.1, the Jarque-Bera (JB) which test for normality or the existence of outliers or extreme values among the variables are normally distributed at 1% level of significance. This means that any variables with outlier are not likely to distort our conclusion and are therefore reliable for drawing generalization.

Correlation Analysis

In examining the relationship among the variables, we employed the Pearson correlation coefficient (correlation matrix) and the results are presented in table 4.2

Table 4.2

Correlation Matrix				
	CURRATIO	QUICKRATIO	TODEBT2TOASS	ROA
CURRATIO	1.00			
QUICKRATIO	0.99	1.00		
TODEBT2TOASS	0.21	0.21	1.00	
ROA	-0.03	-0.03	0.35	1.00

Source: Author (2016)

The use of correlation matrix in most regression analysis is to check for multicollinearity and to explore the association between each explanatory variable and the dependent variable. Table 4.2 focuses on the correlation between corporate profitability (ROA) and working capital management (CURRATIO, QUICKRATIO and TODEBT2TOASS).

The findings from the correction matrix table, shows that there is a strong positive association between current ratio and

quick ratio (0.99). This clearly shows that current ratio and quick ratio indicate the ability of administrators to meet their obligations with its liquid assets. In the case of total debt to total asset (TODEBT2TOASS, current ratio = 0.21, quick ratio = 0.21) we observed that, total debt to total asset was positively and weakly associated with current ratio and quick ratio. While return on asset (ROA, current ratio = -0.03, quick ratio = -0.03 and total debt to total asset = 0.35) are

negatively and weakly association with current ratio and quick ratio. However, are positively and weakly associated with total debt to total asset.

In checking for multicollinearity, we notice that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated. This means that there is the absence of multicollinearity problem in our model. Multicollinearity between explanatory variables may result to wrong signs or implausible magnitudes, in the estimated model coefficients, and the bias of the standard errors of the coefficients.

Table 4.3 Panel regression result

	Aprior Sign	ROA (OLS Pooled)	ROA (Fixed Effect)	ROA (Random Effect)
C		0.12 (3.14) [0.00]*	0.05 (1.83) [0.07]***	0.07 (1.69) [0.09]**
CURRATIO	+	-0.46 (-1.20) [0.23]	0.02 (0.83) [0.09]***	-0.15 (-0.53) [0.59]
QUICKRATIO	+	0.46 (1.19) [0.23]	0.02 (-0.07) [0.09]***	0.15 (0.54) [0.59]
TODEBT2TOASS	+	0.26 (3.32) [0.00]*	0.42 (5.28) [0.00]*	0.36 (5.08) [0.00]*
R-Squared		0.16	0.77	0.30
Adj-R-Squared		0.12	0.64	0.26
F-Statistic		3.82 [0.01]*	5.97 [0.00]*	8.63 [0.00]*
Hausman Test				6.09 [0.10]
N(n)		63(21)	63(21)	63(21)

Source: Author 2016

Note: (1) Parentheses () are t-statistic while bracket [] are p-values

(2) * 1%, ** 5% and *** 10% level of significance

In testing for the cause-effect relationship between the dependent and independent variables in corporate profitability, we reported pooled and panel analysis. This study adopted the three widely used pooled and panel data regression models (fixed effect and panel data estimation techniques). The difference in these models is based on the assumptions made about the explanatory variables and cross

Regression Results

However, to examine the impact relationships between the dependent variables corporate profitability and working capital management and to also test our formulated hypotheses, we used a panel data regression analysis since the data had both time series (2012 to 2014) and cross-sectional properties (21 administrators). The panel data regression results are presented and discussed below.

sectional error term. The results would be more appealing statistically in the context of difference in our sampled administrators.

In table 4.3, we presented an OLS pooled regression and two panel data estimation techniques (fixed effect and panel data estimator). The three results revealed difference in their coefficients magnitude, signs and number of significant variables.

This clearly shows that pooled OLS regression does not reflect the heterogeneity in the sampled administrators. This effect is reflected in the two panel data regression results. In selecting from the two panel data models, the Hausman test was conducted and the result shows that we should accept H_0 (adopt fixed effect model and reject random effect model). This means that we adopt, interpret and draw policy recommendation from the fixed effect panel data regression results.

Following the above, we will discuss the fixed effect panel regression result from Table 4.3. In Table 4.3, the R-squared and adjusted R-squared values were (0.77) and (0.64). These indicate that all independent variables jointly explain about 77% of the systematic variations in corporate profitability of our sampled administrators over the three-year period (2012 – 2014). The above average R-squared value is realistic as it clearly shows corporate profitability and its interaction with working capital management. The F-statistics (5.97) and its p-value (0.00) show that the corporate profitability fixed effect regression model is generally significant and well specified. The F-statistic also shows that the overall corporate profitability fixed effect regression model is significant at 1% levels.

In addition to the above, the specific empirical finding from each explanatory variable from fixed effect regression model is provided as follows:

Current ratio (CURRATIO), based on the coefficient of 0.02 and p-value 0.09 appears to have a positive influence on our sampled fund administrators, corporate profitability was statistically significant at

10% since its p-value was greater than 0.05. This result therefore, suggests that we should reject hypothesis one (H_1), which stated that, there is no significant effect of current ratio on corporate profitability. This means that Nigeria pension administrators are utilizing its working capital (current asset) efficiently to pay its short term and long-term obligations, with positive influence on corporate profitability and conform to a priori expectation. This finding like similar studies Sing & Penny 2008, Binti and Mohd saads' 2010 in Pouraghajan and Emamgholipourarchi 2012, Ikpefan, ., Ailemen and Owolabi 2014 confirms that working capital management effects corporate profitability positively as it is generally indicator of good short-term financial strength of firms.

Quick ratio (QUICKRATIO), based on the coefficient of 0.02 and p-value 0.09 appears to have a positive influence on our sampled fund administrators, corporate profitability and was statistically significant at 10% since its p-value was greater than 0.05. This result therefore, suggests that we should reject hypothesis two (H_2), which stated that, there is no significant effect of quick ratio on corporate profitability. This means that Nigeria pension administrators are utilizing its working capital (cash and cash equivalents, trade and other receivables etc) efficiently to pay its short-term obligations, with positive influence on corporate profitability and conform to a priori expectation. This finding like similar studies Smith & Begemann 1997, Ikpefan, Ailemen & Owolabi 2014, Raheman & Nasr, 2007, Ajibolade & Sankay 2013 confirms that working capital management effects corporate profitability

positively as increasing quick ratio generally indicates that a company is experiencing solid top-line growth, quickly converting receivables into cash, and easily able to cover its financial obligations

Total debt to total assets (TODEBT2TOASS), based on the coefficient of 0.42 and p-value 0.00 appears to have a positive influence on our sampled fund administrators, corporate profitability and was statistically significant at 1% since its p-value was 0.00. This result therefore, suggests that we should reject hypothesis three (H_3), which stated that, there is no significant effect of total debt to total assets on corporate profitability. This means that Nigeria pension administrators have a minimum risk as associated working capital operations, with this minimum risk it shows that administrators have the ability to pay off its liabilities with its assets. With positive influence on corporate profitability and conform to a priori expectation, this finding like similar studies Gill, et al., 2011, Abbasali & Milda 2012 confirms that debt ratio effects corporate profitability positively showing a company's ability to pay off its liabilities with its assets.

5. Conclusion and recommendations

Results from the study indicate that there is significant effect of working capital management on corporate profitability. This is consistent with the findings of Lazaridis & Tryfonidis 2006 that reported

significant positive relationship between working capital management and profitability, stating that managers could create value for shareholders by handling correctly the cash conversion cycle and by keeping each different component to an optimum level. Pouraghajan & Emamgholipourarchi 2012 that stated a significant relationship between the working capital management and profitability, as Pakistani companies correlated heavily on current assets to maximize profits. They provide evidence that managers may enhance the profitability of their firms through proper working capital management.

In addition, the study reveals a positive significant effect of current ratio on quick ratio at 10% level of significant. The results imply that current and quick ratio affects profitability, as Nigeria pension administrators are utilizing its working capital efficiently to pay its short-term obligations. However, total debt to total assets has a positive relationship at 1% level of significant; it means that Nigeria pension administrators have a minimum risk as associated working capital operations, with the commission investment guidelines, the minimum risk shows that administrators have the ability to pay off its liabilities with its assets.

Therefore, the study recommends that administrators should continue to utilize its working capital efficiently to increase profitability, pay its short-term and long-term obligations while maintaining minimum risk with its assets.

Reference

Abbasali P. & Milad E. (2012) Impact of Working Capital Management on Profitability and Market Evaluation: Evidence from Tehran Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*. 3(10) 311-318

Abdul G. K. (2010). The Relationship of Capital Structure Decisions with Firm Performance: A Study of the Engineering Sector of Pakistan. *COMSATS Institute of Information Technology, Vehari*

Ajibolade O. & Sankay C. (2013) Working Capital Management and Financing Decision: Synergetic Effect on Corporate Profitability. *International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences* 2(4) 233 –251.

Albertazzi, U., & Gambacorta, L. (2009) Bank profitability and the business cycle. *Journal of Financial Stability*. 5 393 - 409.

Angahar A. and Agbo A. (2014) Impact of working capital on the profitability of the Nigerian cement industry. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research*, 2(7),17-30

Ani, W., Okwo, I. & Ugwunta, D. (2015) Effects of working capital management on profitability: evidence from the top five beer brewery firms in the world. *Asian Economic and Financial Review* 2(8):966-982

Arshad Z. & Gondal M. Y. (2013) Impact of Working Capital Management on Profitability. A Case of the Pakistan Cement Industry. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research* 5(2) 384 -390

Athanasoglou, P., Brissimis, S., & Delis, M. (2008) Bank-Specific, Industry-Specific and Macroeconomic Determinants of Bank Profitability. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*. 18(2) 121 - 136.

Bourke, P. (1989) Concentration and Other Determinants of bank Profitability in Europe, North America and Australia. *Journal of Banking and Finance*, 13(1) 65 - 79

Deloof, M. (2003). Does Working Capital Management Affect Profitability of Belgian Firms? *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 30(3): 573-585.

Dietrich, A., & Wanzenried, G. (2011) Determinants of Bank Profitability before and During the Crisis: Evidence from Switzerland. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*. 21(3) 307 - 327.

Eljelly, A. (2004). Liquidity – Profitability tradeoff: An empirical investigation in an emergent market. *International Journal of Commerce and Management*, 14(2): 48-61.

Gill, A, Nahum B, & Neil M, (2011). The effect of capital structure on profitability: Evidence from the United States”. *International Journal of Management*, 28(4)3-15.

Gomes D. F. (2013) How Does Working Capital Management Affect Firms’ Profitability? Evidence from Portugal. *Masters thesis LISBOA School of Economics and Management*.

Ikpefan, O. Ailemen & Owolabi F. (2014) Working Capital Management and Profitability of the Manufacturing Sector: An Empirical Investigation of Nestle Nigeria PLC and Cadbury Nigeria PLC. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research* 14 (4) 21 - 27

Kanas, A., Vasiliou, D., & Eritios, N. (2012) Revisiting bank profitability: A semi-parametric approach. *Journal of International Markets, Institutions and Money*. 22 990 - 1005.

- Kulkanya N. (2012) Effects of Working Capital Management on the Profitability of Thai Listed Firms. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, 3(3) 227-232
- Lazaridis, I. & Tryfonidis, D. (2006). "Relationship between Working Capital Management and Profitability of Listed Companies in the Athens Stock Exchange". *Journal of Financial Management and Analysis*. 19 (1), 26 – 35.
- Markowitz H. (1952) Portfolio Selection. *The Journal of Finance* 7 (1) 77–91
- Millon Cornett, M., Guo, L., Khaksari, S., & Tehranian, H. (2010) The impact of state ownership on performance differences in privately-owned versus state-owned banks: An international comparison. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*. 19 74 – 94
- Ojeani, N (2010) Working capital management and profitability of listed pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria. *A thesis submitted to the school of postgraduate studies, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria*
- Olufemi I. & Olubanjo T. (2009) Working capital management and corporate profitability: evidence from panel data analysis of selected quoted companies in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Business Management* 3(3) 73-84
- Osundina J. (2014) Working capital management and profitability of selected quoted food and beverages manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting Auditing and Finance Research* 2(3) 10-21
- Owolabi S. & Alu C. (2012) Effective working capital management and profitability. *Economics and Finance Review*. 2(6) 55 – 67
- Owolabi, S. A. & Alayemi, S. A. (2010): "The study of working capital management as a financial strategy: A case study of Nestle Nigeria Plc". *Asian journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 2(4).
- Pandey, I. M. (2005). *Financial Management*, (9th Ed). Vikas Publishing, New Delhi
- Park, K., & Weber, W. (2006) Profitability of Korean banks: Test of market structure versus efficient structure. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 58 222 - 239
- Pasiouras, F. & Kosmidou, K. (2007) Factors influencing the profitability of domestic and foreign commercial banks in the European Union. *Research in International Business and Finance*. 21(2) 222 – 237
- Pouraghajan A. & Emamgholipourarchi M. (2012) Impact of Working Capital Management on Profitability and Market Evaluation: Evidence from Tehran Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Business and Social Science* 3 (10)
- Rahema, A., Qayyum, A. & Afza, T. (2011). Sector-wise Performance of Working Capital Management Measures and Profitability Using Ratio Analysis *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business* 3 (8)
- Raheman, A. & Nasr, N. (2007). Working capital management and profitability: Case of Pakistani firms. *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 3(1): 279 - 300.
- Singh, J. P. & Shishir P., (2008). Impact of working capital management in the profitability of Hindalco industries limited" ,*ICFAI Journal of financial Economics* 6 (4), 62-72 .
- Smith, M. B., & Begemann E. (1997). Measuring association between working capital and Return on Investment. *South Africa Journal of Business Management*, 28, (1), 1-5.

Staikouras, C. K., & Wood, G. E. (2004) The Determinants of European Bank Profitability. *International Business and Economics Research Journal*, 3(6) 57 - 68

Tomuleasa I. & Cocris, V. (2014) Measuring the financial performance of the European systemically important banks. *Financial Studies* 4 31-51

Zahra, M & Azam, J (2012) The Relationship between Working Capital Management and Firm Performance: Evidence from Iran. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science* 2(2) 141-146